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Deliverable 2.4.d2

Final BOLD business models for stakeholders

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2 Executive Summary

The vision of openlaws.eu is to make access to justice easier. The project is co-funded by the European Union. The challenge is to make this project sustainable in the long run and to make it independent of public funding. The issue is that legal information is a public good and that it is the duty of governments and the EU themselves to inform citizens and business about the law. In a democracy and under the rule of law everybody should know legislation and case law – or at least have access to it. The question is how can a project that is (at least partially) fulfilling public duties be financed without receiving funding or tax income from the EU or its member states? After all, administrations themselves struggle with financing new solutions for citizens, even though they know which services are needed and which ones would be useful for the citizens and the common market as a whole.

In recent years a new category of start-ups has emerged, the so-called social entrepreneurs. There is no generally-accepted definition of social entrepreneurship, but the general idea behind the concept is that “doing good” and “doing well” can and should be combined. Business mechanisms are introduced in order to solve social problems. Just like open data and open innovation, social entrepreneurship is a topic of high interest, also for the European Commission.¹

Access to justice is a fundamental problem in the European Union. There are over 500 million citizens and over 21 million businesses live, work and operate in 28 jurisdictions, written in 24 official languages. A common market cannot work without a legal system as a basis. For an entrepreneur this means there is a big problem as well as a large potential market. Usually this is a solid basis for a sustainable business model. The entrepreneur creates value and captures part of this value in order to finance the operation of the venture. However, the fact that legal information is supposed to be free leads to considerable restrictions. Still, in the age of the Internet many services and business model innovations have been implemented. In his book “Free”, Chris Anderson describes different ways how “free” can work.

For the research project “openlaws.eu” this means that a “social entrepreneurship” business model can be applied to the project spin-off “openlaws.com”. This spin-off can be built on a social entrepreneurship mind-set and on an online solution that offers free legal information for citizens and businesses that is relevant to their everyday lives. Developing more sophisticated features for experts, researchers, administrations and other power-users will create added value and generate revenues for the spin-off. Additional features will not necessarily all be developed by openlaws.eu or by the project spin-off directly, but may be implemented by third parties, who may know the needs of the users even better than the research openlaws.eu core team or the spin-off team (especially in specific expert domains and in specific legal settings of different jurisdictions). The basis for such third-party applications will be the the aggregated database (the “BOLDbase”).

The openlaws.eu solution that is deployed to users under the EU project funding has reached the level of a working prototype (Technology Readiness Level 6, or “TRL 6”). The strategic business plan foresees additional development activities in a second step, in order to take the research prototype to a fully operational level (TRL 9) and on-going exploitation, is done by the project spin-off “openlaws.com”.²

¹ European Commission, Social Innovation – A Decade of Change (a BEPA Report), 2014, DOI 10.2796/27161, <http://bookshop.europa.eu/> (26.6.2015).

² “openlaws gmbh” was incorporated in January 2015 under Austrian laws as a spin-off of the EU project.

3 Industry and Trend Analysis

3.1 Problem

Do you know the law? There is an enormous amount of legal information out there, both on a national and on a European level. Unfortunately, it is hard to keep an overview. Still, every citizen and every company has to comply with legal obligations and not knowing the law is no excuse, as we all know. Of course, it is also useful to know your rights. After all, the rule of law is a central element of all democratic states. But how can we ensure that citizens and businesses have access to legislation, case law and other legal information, and – equally important – how can we find information that is relevant for our personal situation?

Traditionally, legal experts have been the gatekeepers to legal information. Clients went to see their lawyer in order to get legal advice. This was already true in ancient Rome. In consideration of this, the lawyer was paid on an hourly basis. However, with the rise of technology and with the formation of online communities, things are changing. In the medical field, patients can find health information much more easily than in the past. This obviously does not render medical experts useless. Still, the relation between doctor and patient is currently being re-defined. The same is true in the legal area, as suggested by *Richard Susskind* in a book with the provocative title ‘The end of lawyers?’.³ These developments require lawyers to adapt their practice and opens new opportunities for innovative business models. This does not mean that lawyers will be replaced, but rather that their activities and tools will change. Lawyers should see technology as an opportunity to provide additional and complementary services to their clients. Legal technology is part of the solution, not part of the problem.

Figure 1: Legal technology complementing the lawyer-client relation

Today, we are living in a knowledge society and are overwhelmed by the amount of available data (big data). More and more data sources are currently made available to the public (open data). This information overload needs to be handled by users. We need to get legal information that is “just right” for us. Not enough information, and you run into legal risks and liability, too much information and you get lost. So the problem is how can we manage legal information in the most effective and in the most efficient way? This situation is obviously not entirely new, search engines have been around since the early days of the Internet, and e-mail alert systems are nothing new either. There are legal ICT solutions, operated by governments and the private sector, but such systems are often limited and not taking advantage of the latest technologies, which are available for knowledge management

³ Susskind, Richard, *The End of Lawyers? Rethinking the Nature of Legal Services*, Oxford University Press (2010). See also OpenLaws.eu deliverable D2.3.d1, Socio-Economic Framework for BOLD Stakeholders.

and collaboration.

From a European perspective, the harmonization of the legal systems of 28 EU Member State jurisdictions is a challenge of its own. Legislators need to implement new directives, judges have to rule in line with national and European laws and should ideally consider case law from other member states, and international companies need to know the various rules for all countries in which they are active. Innovative legal ICT tools may help solve these issues.

The legal information problem can be taken even one level higher. Globalisation is leading to the provocative question, whether or not legislation is losing its control function due to the dominance of the economy.⁴ At the same time, the economic crises and financial scandals have led to more regulation in the area of corporate governance.⁵ So there should be a balance between the economy and the law. Transparency and legal information systems can help alleviate this problem.

3.2 End User Needs

Who is interested in legal information anyway? In the first phase of the openlaws.eu project, a lot of effort has been put into stakeholder analysis. Several end-user groups and their needs were identified⁶:

- **Citizens** need easy access to legal information as a first entry point and to find an expert in case further advice is needed.
- **Businesses** need legal information on a regular basis in order to be able to fulfil their obligations and to exercise their rights. The larger the business, the more jurisdictions and the more legal professionals need to be managed.
- **Legal professionals** need expert access to premium content, to increase their productivity and to demonstrate their skills to potential clients. In order to stay competitive, lawyers organize themselves more and more in formal or informal legal networks.
- **Researchers** need access to legislation, case law and premium legal content in order to generate new knowledge. They need to publish and disseminate their findings. Open access publication is required in many publicly funded research projects.
- **Public bodies and civil servants** have to inform citizens and have to use legislation, case law and commentary in their own daily work.

Depending on the level of legal expertise, users have different needs when it comes to ICT-enabled legal information systems. While legal professionals seek legal expert systems that provide in-depth knowledge, citizens and businesses require easy-to-use systems that provide a quick overview. However, other markets show that the lines between pure expert systems and information tools for the broad public are blurring. One example may be Google Patent Search or Google Scholar for Case Law, which have evolved from the general Google search engine and which are used by professionals and laypersons alike (see also the trend “more-for-less” below).

⁴ European Forum Alpbach 2014, Law at the Crossroads: How Will Law Develop in the 21st Century?, <http://www.alpbach.org>.

⁵ OECD principles on corporate governance: <http://www.oecd.org/daf/ca/oecdprinciplesofcorporategovernance.htm>: The corporate governance framework should promote transparent and efficient markets, be consistent with the rule of law and clearly articulate the division of responsibilities among different supervisory, regulatory and enforcement authorities.

⁶ See openlaws.eu deliverable 1.1.d1 State-of-the-art report for legal, social and business aspects of re-use of legal information and deliverable 4.1.d3 Stakeholder handbook, www.openlaws.eu.

3.3 Trends

Legal professionals are not often early adopters of new trends and technologies. Arguably, they start to use new technology only together with the late majority or may even be considered laggards.⁷ Adopting new technology earlier or later is not a question of right or wrong. There are sound reasons why the legal profession is very careful before jumping on the bandwagon. For example, privacy and data security are issues that may matter even more to legal professionals compared to other businesses. Clients expect the highest trust level when consulting a legal expert.

Figure 2: Adopting new technology

However, there are also other professions where trust and quality play a big role. Other industries have proven that innovative Internet services can cope with such challenges. With more and more digital natives coming out of universities, ICT-enabled services are likely to become more common in the legal area. This can already be observed in the USA where legal tech companies are highly active. Looking at Silicon Valley, a full range of legal tech start-ups can be observed.⁸ Venture capitalists have already successfully financed such legal tech companies.⁹

In comparison to traditional law firms, businesses are more open to innovative solutions, especially if they help them run their core business better or if they reduce the risks or the costs for the company. With an abundant number of new Internet services, citizens are also used to explore innovative solutions, especially if they are provided free of charge and if they help them make their lives easier.

A few general trends can be observed in the area of ICT. All of these are visible in legal information technologies. However, bearing the progress of such trends in other markets in mind, it becomes clearer where the road of legal tech will lead us.

⁷ Susskind, Richard, *The End of Lawyers? Rethinking the Nature of Legal Services*, Oxford University Press (2010). This is also in line with the OpenLaws.eu field research, interviews and focus groups. Even lawyers consider themselves often as laggards with respect to new technology.

⁸ The openlaws.eu team attended the Stanford CodeX Future Law conference in April 2015 and conducted interviews with several start-ups in the San Francisco Bay Area.

⁹ See for example Techcrunch, *Legal Tech Startup Casetext Raises \$7 Million Series A Round Led By Union Square Ventures* <http://techcrunch.com/2015/02/03/legal-tech-startup-casetext-raises-7-million-series-a-round-led-by-union-square-ventures/> (26.6.2015).

3.3.1 Digitalization, Social Networks and Mobility

As everywhere, digitalization is a so-called megatrend. Legal databases replace traditional libraries, e-mails have replaced most letters (with the exception of “official” letters from/to authorities). Social networks are everywhere, and even if there are only few dedicated social networks in the legal market, people are used to creating connections with each other (e.g. via LinkedIn or Facebook). Smartphones and tablet PCs make it easier for everybody to access ICT services anytime and anywhere.

3.3.2 Mass Customization

Mass customization is a trend that is used almost in every online-based service in order to provide services in accordance with the personal profile and the personal needs of users (e.g. a personal dashboard for the user after log-in). Customized services help users to save time and to increase their productivity.

3.3.3 Open Innovation

Open innovation is a paradigm that assumes that firms can and should use external ideas as well as internal ideas, and internal and external paths to market, as the firms look to advance their technology.¹⁰ On the other hand, knowledge that is generated within the company should be licensed out in order to enable third parties to build additional services, which might address the customer needs even better or in another segment. The concept has become more and more popular in recent years in order to create solutions that are close to the users. At a European level, this trend is for example being analysed by the Open Innovation Strategy Policy Group (OISPG) of the European Commission.¹¹

Figure 3: Open innovation funnel

3.3.4 Open Data and Big Data

More and more governments make information available as ‘open data’ so that it can be re-used by citizens and businesses, who are supposed to build new user-friendly services on top of these resources. The Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive supports this trend.¹² Legislation and case law are well suited to be made available as open data, in particular because everybody is supposed to know the law.

¹⁰ Chesbrough, Henry William (1 March 2003). *Open Innovation: The new imperative for creating and profiting from technology*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.

¹¹ OISPG, <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/open-innovation-strategy-and-policy-group/> (26.6.2015).

¹² Directive 2003/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 November 2003, on the re-use of public sector information, amended by Directive 2013/37/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 (PSI Directive), <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CONSLEG:2003L0098:20130717:EN:PDF> (26.6.2015).

Big data refers to large amounts of data that can be analysed to gain new insights. People or machines can either create such big data. In case of legislation and case law, there are lots of documents (usually in text format), which may be analysed and linked. For example, typical patterns or relations between documents can be discovered.

The European Commission considers both open data and big data as important trends. Accordingly they are part of the ‘Digital Agenda for Europe’.¹³

3.3.5 Innovative Business Models

Creating innovative business models (in particular for global competitiveness) is a trend of its own, which is also monitored by the European Commission. This trend includes the use of innovative methods for companies to develop their business through the use of ICT and/or social media for internationalisation.¹⁴ With more and more introduction of ICT in the legal market, this trend will also lead to disruptive business models in the area of law.

3.3.6 Social Entrepreneurship

There is no clear definition of the term “social entrepreneurship” and the term is often at the centre of lively discussions. One attempt at defining it has been undertaken in the Harvard Business Review by Roger L. Martin and Sally Osberg: “The social entrepreneur should be understood as someone who targets an unfortunate but stable equilibrium that causes the neglect, marginalization, or suffering of a segment of humanity; who brings to bear on this situation his or her inspiration, direct action, creativity, courage, and fortitude; and who aims for and ultimately affects the establishment of a new stable equilibrium that secures permanent benefit for the targeted group and society at large.”¹⁵

Social entrepreneurship has become even more famous in the light of the economic crises. It is considered as one element to solve pressing social problems, not only in Europe but on a global level.¹⁶ In recent years it has also become clearer that social entrepreneurship is not a contradiction, but that there are ways to make it work in practice.¹⁷

3.3.7 More-for-Less

Another trend is to receive ‘more-for-less’.¹⁸ Citizens and businesses alike are used to receive more performance for a much smaller price. This trend is of course a problem for industries with only limited economies of scale or economies of scope. The more-for-less challenge is also an issue in the legal market, when clients expect more legal advice for less money (also because of their own need to reduce costs in order to remain competitive).

¹³ See <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/content-and-media/data> (26.6.2015).

¹⁴ See European Commission, Business Innovation Observatory, Trend report - Design for innovation, smart living and innovative business models; how to scale-up success, March 2014, <http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/policies/innovation/policy/business-innovation-observatory/files/02-design-for-innovation-smart-living-and-innovative-business-models.pdf> (26.6.2015).

¹⁵ Roger L. Martin & Sally Osberg, Social Entrepreneurship: The Case for Definition, http://www.ssireview.org/articles/entry/social_entrepreneurship_the_case_for_definition/ (26.6.2015).

¹⁶ European Commission, Social Innovation – A Decade of Changes, BEPA Report, <http://bookshop.europa.eu/> (26.6.2015).

¹⁷ Thompson, J. D., & MacMillan, I. C. (2010). Making Social Ventures Work. Harvard Business Review.

¹⁸ See for example Matthias Horx, <http://www.zukunftsinstitut.de> (26.6.2015).

Figure 4: Transition in the area of legal information services

In the past users had the choice between “free and simple” or “paid and advanced”. As we can see in other markets, the lines are blurring. Users often get free and easy services that also offer advanced features. This has also become possible because of innovative business models (see above).

3.4 Innovative Legal Tech Service Categories

Taking a look at the legal tech market of today, several segments can be identified (not exhaustive). All of them are supposed to make access to legal information easier. Often the different categories are combined in one system.

Category	Description
Legislation databases	Databases to access legislation, typically operated by governments
Case law databases	Databases to access case law, typically operated by governments and/or publishers
Literature databases	Databases to access literature, typically operated by publishers
Registers	Registers to find information on companies, patents, land, etc.
Case management	Services to manage different cases
Contract databases	Services to manage contracts
Electronic filing tools	Services for electronic filing of documents, e.g. in at court or at public administrations
Communication tools	Services for communication between different parties, in particular legal professionals
Dispute resolution tools	Services that can be used to solve conflicts between two parties

	without having to go to court
Document assembly tools	Services to create new documents, e.g. in legislative processes
eDiscovery tools	Services that help to collect relevant information, in particular in cases of litigation or governmental investigation

Table 1: Legal Tech Service Categories

Despite the special requirements of the legal field, it is not necessary to re-invent the wheel. Often standard software is available and can be adapted for introduction into the legal market. Many components are even available as open source software.

3.5 Benchmarking and Case Studies

Legal tech is already a trend in the USA. Successful start-ups show that value for users can be created and that part of this value can be captured to make their businesses successful and sustainable. Open data in Europe is an opportunity to build similar solutions also in the European Union, which are likely to have some functionality in common, but which may also be different in many aspects, as a result of the different legal systems. In this section a few selected cases from the USA and Canada will be presented. In addition, the open data project Eurocases will be showcased – a project that has emerged from the EU project EU Cases.

3.5.1 Google Scholar - Case Law Search

Google operates its own case law search.¹⁹ As a subset of Google Scholar, users can search content with the well-established Google user interface. Compared to the “normal” Google search, Google Scholar has a few special features, like the integration of a citation count for academic papers and the option to save search results under “My Citations”. This helps to create a personalized case law portfolio. Users can also create alerts for certain search terms. In the Google Case Law Search, users can also specify which data sources (courts) should be searched. For example, only US Federal Courts, the Supreme Court or the 9th Circuit, CD California, etc. can be selected. This filter helps to narrow down the search results. Google Scholar can also be used to find legal publications and journal papers and provides a few statistics on them.

¹⁹ <http://scholar.google.com/> (26.6.2015).

Figure 5: Google Case Law Search

Google’s business model is mainly based on advertising.²⁰ Traditionally, Google is focusing on very large and broad markets and on services that are used on a daily basis.²¹ This may explain why there have not been major changes to the google Case Law Search. The service has remained stable during the duration of the openlaws EU project, without any obvious updates or changes. It is clear however, that Google has the resources and the knowledge to transform legal search entirely – provided that Google decides to do so. Google has the knowledge on search technology, on link and reference recognition, on thesauri and semantics, on translations, internationalisation and so forth. One might argue: The question is not if Google can disrupt legal information technology, but only if it is a priority for Google to do so.

But even if Google is not focusing on law directly, Google invests in legal tech. Google Ventures has made an investment in Rocket Lawyer.²²

3.5.2 Rocket Lawyer

Founded in 2008 in San Francisco, RocketLawyer²³ is a legal tech company with them vision to change things by making legal services affordable, simple and available to more people than ever before. The service helps to create legal documents for businesses and citizens, helps to register a company and puts users in contact with lawyers.

²⁰ <https://www.google.co.uk/intl/en/adwords/> (31.3.2016).

²¹ Jarvis, J. (2011). What would Google do?: Reverse-engineering the fastest growing company in the history of the world. Harper Business.

²² Fisher, Daniel. Google Jumps Into Online-Law Business With Rocket Lawyer. Forbes. August 11, 2011, <http://www.forbes.com/sites/danielfisher/2011/08/11/google-jumps-into-online-law-business-with-rocket-lawyer/#4988230045a7> (31.3.2016).

²³ <https://www.rocketlawyer.com/> (26.6.2015).

Figure 6: Rocket Lawyer

Rocket Lawyer has received \$43 million USD in funding and generates over \$20 million in annual revenue.²⁴ The services are based on a monthly subscription fee, that can be cancelled at any time. The switch to a low-priced “first-one-free” and subsequent subscription model was made after the recession of 2008, resulting in a high increase of revenue.²⁵

3.5.3 Casetext

The mission of Casetext is to pair free legal research and publishing so users can search US state and federal cases, statutes, and regulations, for free, annotated by insights from attorneys, law firms, and academics.²⁶ The company is aggregating legal content from different sources and lets the community work with it. Expert users can publish comments and summaries to build their reputation. In this respect, Casetext is probably the closest related US service.

The ultimate business model of Casetext is not clear yet. However, this is not uncommon in the US and investors still see a large potential in the venture. As reported by famous TechCrunch, the Silicon Valley start-up has successfully raised 7 millions USD in a series A round in 2015.²⁷ This was just before the openlaws team met Casetext during the Future Law Conference 2015 in Stanford, USA. As quoted in the TechCrunch article, the major problem for Casetext is to encourage the right people so that the community is growing.

²⁴ Rubin, Courtney. Big Money for Cheap Legal Services. Inc. Magazine. January 5, 2012, [http://www.inc.com/courtney-rubin/rocket-lawyer-raises-\\$11-million.html](http://www.inc.com/courtney-rubin/rocket-lawyer-raises-$11-million.html) (31.3.2016).

²⁵ Klein, Karen. To Beat the Recession, Reinvent Your Business. Bloomberg. October 23, 2009, http://www.businessweek.com/smallbiz/content/oct2009/sb20091023_229168.htm (31.3.2016).

²⁶ <http://www.casetext.com/> (26.6.2015).

²⁷ <http://techcrunch.com/2015/02/03/legal-tech-startup-casetext-raises-7-million-series-a-round-led-by-union-square-ventures/> (26.3.2016).

Figure 7: Casetext

3.5.4 RavellLaw

RavellLaw²⁸ is another US start-up from Silicon Valley. Ravel Law is a new legal search, analytics, and visualization platform. Ravel enables lawyers to find, contextualize, and interpret information that turns legal data into legal insights. Ravel's tools include data-driven, interactive visualizations and analytics. In 2012, Ravel spun out of Stanford University's Law School, Computer Science Department, and d.school²⁹, with the support of CodeX (Stanford's Center for Legal Informatics).

The interactive graphical presentations provided by RavellLaw are a very good example for visualization in law. The picture shows how cases are connected via citations and calculates the impact of a case based on the incoming references. Cases that are cited more frequently are displayed as larger bubbles in the chart. The user can navigate through the chart by clicking on the bubbles. The related cases are shown on the right side as a preview. The user can then select to view the full text.

RavellLaw is offering free and premium products (open, advanced, elite and enterprise). However, prices are not yet displayed on the website. User have to contact the team for an offer.

It is noteworthy that RavellLaw is investing large amounts of money into scanning US case-law. This is a joint effort, together with Harvard Law School.³⁰ The content is published for free on the RavellLaws website. Even though this action is a private initiative from a leading US university and a start-up, the results are the same as intended by the European PSI Directive. Public sector information is opened up. However, as reported in the New York Times, the data is currently only available for research and non-profit organisations. The data

²⁸ <https://www.ravellaw.com/> (26.6.2015).

²⁹ <https://dschool.stanford.edu> (26.3.2016).

³⁰ <http://today.law.harvard.edu/harvard-law-school-launches-free-the-law-project-with-ravel-law-to-digitize-us-case-law-provide-free-access/> (26.3.2016).

will be withheld from other commercial groups for a period of eight years.³¹

Figure 8: RavellLaw

3.5.5 CanLII and CanLII Connects

CanLII (Canadian Legal Information Institute) provides access to court judgments, tribunal decisions, statutes and regulations from all Canadian jurisdictions. CanLII is a non-profit organization that has been engaged by the law societies of Canada that are members of the Federation of Law Societies of Canada to establish, operate, maintain and provide to the law societies a website dedicated to providing continuous access to a virtual library of Canadian legal information. Its goal is to make Canadian law accessible on the Internet.³²

CanLII is a fully operational legal information platform. The functionality is up-to-date and very user-friendly. The two outstanding things about CanLII are however its unique funding and the community-functionality in an official legal information platform.

The website is funded by Canada's lawyers and notaries and provides free access to legal information for the benefit of everybody. Funding for specific projects such as expansion of historical databases has been received from provincial law foundations and other sources. In a way, the development of this platform was "crowd-funded". Lawyers and notaries teamed up and financed the venture. The platform was not closed and access is not limited to paying members, but is available to the public, in accordance with the "Free Access to Law Movement" principles. It seems that making the platform open and available is not an issue for the lawyers and notaries. People still seek advice, because the platform will not solve cases.

The second remarkable approach of CanLII is CanLII Connects.³³ This add-on to CanLII was created to make it faster and easier for legal professionals and the public to access high-

³¹ http://www.nytimes.com/2015/10/29/us/harvard-law-library-sacrifices-a-trove-for-the-sake-of-a-free-database.html?_r=0 (26.3.2016).

³² <http://www.canlii.org/en/info/about.html> (26.3.2016).

³³ <http://canliiconnects.org/> (26.6.2015).

quality legal commentary on Canadian court decisions. CanLII connects brings together lawyers, scholars and others with professional competency in legal analysis to share their insights and form collective opinions. To maintain quality, only the community of registered members are permitted to submit content, offer comments or up-vote the commentary and summaries found on the site. Just like CanLII, CanLII Connects is open and free.

Figure 9: CanLII Connects

3.5.6 EU Cases – Eurocases

EuroCases is a multilingual web-based legal informational service providing access to case law of selected jurisdictions in Europe related to the application of European Union law. It is maintained and updated by the Bulgarian legal information provider APIS Europe JSC. EuroCases builds upon the achievements of the EUCases project supported by the European Commission.³⁴

EuroCases is a research tool for EU law and multinational case law for lawyers, notaries and legal scholars. They can access case law from different jurisdictions via one single access point. Users can filter search results based on country, area of law and source of law.

A limited demo version of the service is live, the full version requires a subscription. One license for 12 months costs 340 Euros, two licenses 480 Euros, three licenses 580 Euros and ten licenses 1,200 Euros. An academic license pack with twenty licenses is available for 480 Euros.

³⁴ <http://eucases.eu> (26.3.2016).

Figure 10: EuroCases

4 Description of the Venture

4.1 Vision

The vision of openlaws is to provide access to legal information and legal experts in the most user-friendly way possible, both on a national and on a European level.

Legal information means primary sources of the law, i.e. legislation and case law, as well as secondary sources, i.e. literature and commentary. These two categories of sources will be complemented with a social layer, i.e. the legal community in its broadest sense.

Figure 11: openlaw.eu Pillars

Citizens will learn more about their rights. For companies it will be easier to act in accordance with the law. Legal experts can demonstrate their knowledge and intensify the customer-relationship. Publishers can integrate their premium legal content via open interfaces. Governments can support openlaws and the creation of a community-driven legal knowledge base by making even more data sources available as open data.

For this purpose, openlaws is building a cloud-based online service, where users can search for legal information, organize it the way they need it (e.g. by creating personalized folders, by adding tags, highlights and comments, etc.), and share it with others, either entirely openly or in private groups.

Figure 12: Social and institutional layers

The aim of openlaws is to become a self-sustaining ICT service. This means that the platform will create value for its users and that part of this added-value will be captured by the operators of the openlaws platform for further development and operation.

Notwithstanding the foregoing, openlaws is addressing a need of European society as a whole. The project is fostering transparency, collaboration and participation in the area of law and therefore directly supporting open governance.³⁵ With this background, openlaws can be considered a social venture.³⁶

openlaws is built on open design principles:

- Open data: Legislation and case law that are made available by governments are integrated into openlaws.
- Open innovation: Users can contribute data and metadata in the form of summaries, user-generated collections, links, tags and highlights, which will lead to a community generated legal information system.
- Open source software: openlaws is built on top of open source software components. It will provide open interfaces, so that third parties can join the open innovation process.

4.2 Services

In the first phase of the project, the openlaws team has identified core services, which are relevant for citizens, businesses and legal experts and which promise to be highly beneficial

³⁵ See European Commission, A Vision for Public Services, , <http://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/vision-public-services> (26.6.2015).

³⁶ See European Commission, Social Business Initiative – Creating a favourable climate for social enterprises, key stakeholders in the social economy and innovation, http://ec.europa.eu/internal_market/social_business/docs/COM2011_682_en.pdf (26.6.2015).

to the evolution of social legal information networks. These are:

- a) an easy-to-use integrated European legislation and case law search,
- b) the ability to customize legal information according to individual requirements and to share it with peers and
- c) the ability to make advanced expert profiles available to the public.

While basic search features and content under Creative-Commons licenses can be offered for free, advanced features and copyright protected premium content (in collaboration with external partners like publishers) will be offered under a transparent pricing scheme in order to make the openlaws platform sustainable.

Figure 13: Business Model Canvas³⁷ for openlaws.eu

4.2.1 Free Legal Search

First and foremost, it is important to be able to explore the law and to find relevant information. There are already national governmental databases as well as commercial databases operated by publishers, but there are few systems that link national databases with European databases or with databases of other EU Member States. With a growing European integration, it is becoming more and more important to manage national and European legislation and case law at the same time.

While legal professionals are typically using (expert) search functionalities to find what they need ('search-field approach'), citizens and businesses will need a more structured approach to be able to browse through legal topics ('directory approach'). In addition, recommendation systems will ensure that the users find related legal information.³⁸

³⁷ A. Osterwalder, Yves Pigneur, Alan Smith (2010). Business Model Generation, self published; <http://businessmodelalchemist.com/tools> (26.6.2015).

³⁸ Winkels, Boer, Vredregt, Someren (2014), Towards a Legal Recommender System, JURIX 2014 conference

4.2.2 Premium Expert Features

In the future openlaws.eu may come up with premium features that are used by legal professionals. These services may include advanced search features and point-in-time searches. Extended multi-lingual features may be another important aspect.

These expert services can either be developed by the openlaws core team in order to create an additional revenue stream or by third parties via the “licensing out” model (see next point).

4.2.3 Aggregated Data

The platform will aggregate legislation and case law from different open data repositories from the EU. In addition, user-generated content and metadata will be collected. This information will be stored in the Big Open Legal Database (“BOLDbase”) and is the basis for the services described above.

In accordance with open innovation principles, the BOLDbase will be also made available to third party projects. Such third parties can then build their own services on top of it. Rather than having to aggregate the legal data themselves, third parties can immediately use the whole database or parts of it (e.g. the EU and all integrated Member States or the EU and only one Member State). This will reduce risk, costs and time to market. In the following section a few suggestions for third party services are outlined.

Figure 1: openlaws.eu BOLDbase

4.3 Third Party Services and Business Models

openlaws is designed so that third parties may build their own legal ICT business models on top of the openlaws infrastructure. For example, expert systems, translation tools for law, analytics or content promotion services could be created for desktop or mobile applications. A few ideas are presented, as a spark for inspiration. The openlaws project will support third-party applications, both from research or from business partners.

4.3.1 Expert Systems

One implementation of a third-party services could be a legal expert system with a special

proceeding (JURIX 2014 award), <http://jurix.nl> (26.6.2015).

focus on international and comparative law. Legal professionals but also international businesses who are active in two or more jurisdictions or who work on cross-border cases are an interesting target group. The third-party service could foster comparative law and show cases that are highly relevant in both countries.

Reference is made to the EuroCases service, that has evolved from the EUCases project. This service is already moving in this direction and offers expert search for selected jurisdictions, related to European case law and legislation (see EuroCases case study).

4.3.2 Visualization and Text Analysis

Visualization of legislation and case law can be a useful tool for navigation through large amounts of legal information. Linked case law with all its references and citations is a promising candidate for graphical representations, other than in traditional text form. The openlaws Neo4J graph database already contains linked case law. There are visualization software libraries under open source license which could be applied.

The business model for such visualizations may not be clear yet. Would users be willing to pay for an additional stand-alone visual service? From what we have learned during the IRIS conferences 2015 and 2016 in Salzburg, expert users still seem to be reluctant. So for the time being – until the visualizations are actually there – this field may be a playground for university exploration. Exploitation on the market may follow later.

RavelLaw is a good example for visualization in the USA. Cases are represented in an interactive chart as bubbles. The size of the bubbles varies depending on the number of incoming references (see RavelLaw case study). The start-up has recently also introduced “analytics” for law, which brings us to the next category of potential services.

4.3.3 Analytics

A large database with a lot of content is predestined for data and big data analysis. Even though legal databases cannot be considered big data under today’s definitions (volume, velocity, variety), but the amounts of text are still “too big” for being simply read, monitored and analysed by humans. New services could take the database, analyse it (usually it is text) and transform raw data into digested information. For example, statistic could reveal where breaches of the law are in particular costly and pose a balance sheet risk for a corporation. Legal experts would probably immediately refer to competition and anti-trust law, based on their experience – but what about copyright or privacy? How would you measure that? Another question are statistics on the probable outcome of a case. How are my chances to win or lose?

In fact, these kinds of services, which could be built on top of the openlaws database, will raise ethical concerns. The economic analysis of the law is a highly interesting but controversial topic.

Nonetheless, services are already on the market. In the USA Lex Machina, a LexisNexis company,³⁹ is offering analytics on intellectual property (IP) law. For example, the service will tell you the chances for approval of your patent application. Another US service is Premonition.⁴⁰ The service provides statistic about which lawyers win before which judge – on a statistical basis.

³⁹ <https://lexmachina.com> (26.3.2016).

⁴⁰ <http://premonition.ai> (26.3.2016).

4.3.4 Legal Intelligence

Wouldn't it be nice if you could ask the machine a legal question and it could come up with the answer right away? This is of course science fiction, but large players are already working on training machines. Data sources are an important basis.

For example, IBM Watson⁴¹ is a platform for “cognitive business”. IBM Watson is a technology platform that uses natural language processing and machine learning to reveal insights from large amounts of unstructured data. ROSS⁴² is a legal service built on top of IBM Watson. The value proposition is that users can ask questions in plain English and ROSS then reads through the entire body of law and returns a cited answer and topical readings from legislation, case law and secondary sources. In addition, ROSS monitors the law to notify users of new court decisions.

4.3.5 Translation Tools for Legislation and Case Law

Language is a classic barrier in the legal domain, especially in the European Union, with its 24 official languages. Even though slightly less challenging compared to answering legal questions, this task is still extremely complex. Legal language is special. The style of formulations and expressions and the special terms used are different than the average language. In addition, high quality translations are needed. It is just not enough to get the meaning of an article, the legal expert needs to understand the smallest differences in a legal text. A machine-translation may just not be enough to reach this high level.

Still, automated machine translation could be a first step in the right direction. While the machine makes the first attempt, humans could do the fine-tuning in a second step. The aggregated openlaws database could be a good starting point.

4.3.6 Specific Legal Applications

Each domain of the law has its specifics. There are legal experts in each and every domain of the law, from family law to environmental law and criminal law. While openlaws is covering the basic legal texts for all domains, more specific and more sophisticated solutions could be built for each domain.

For example, a mobile for construction law could be created and combined with other services, for example Open Street Maps. Building companies and architects could be a target group for such an application, allowing them to check the applicable law on-site easily.

4.3.7 Promotion of Premium Content

Producing commentary about the law is a viable business model. Commercial publishers have been applying this model since ages. Today, this editorial work is combined and extended by many publishers with legal services as mentioned above. Publishers already have primary sources of the law (legislation and case law) in their systems.

Still, openlaws could be used by publishers as an additional aggregated data source (for example when they want to include other jurisdictions), or for promoting their content. Premium content could appear within openlaws right next to the primary sources.

With upcoming open access publications, this model may become even more attractive. Authors pay the publishers directly; the publication is then freely available on the Internet. For spreading the publication in the legal community, openlaws may be the right channel for a publisher to support its business model.

⁴¹ <http://www.ibm.com/smarterplanet/us/en/ibmwatson/> (26.3.2016).

⁴² <http://www.rossintelligence.com> (26.3.2016).

4.4 Novelty of the Service

openlaws.eu is different and new compared to previous legal information systems. The ‘open’ approach of the system refers to the usage of open innovation, open data and open source software. These concepts are not simply ‘buzz-words’, but actually describe the novelty and the unique selling proposition (USP) of the system. Rather than operating top-down, openlaws is actively engaging the community.

- **Open innovation** means that users are not only passive consumers of the platform, but also active producers at the same time (‘prosumers’). While legal information systems in the past have been closed, users of openlaws contribute to the system. They generate both content (e.g. the summary of a case) and metadata (e.g. by adding tags and keywords). At the same time a network between the users and the legal content is created.
- **Open data and open data business model** means that the system re-uses legal information that is provided by governments. By creating added-value on top of such (mostly free) resource, openlaws is also one of the first ventures that is fully taking advantage of an open data business model.
- **Open source software** means that system is designed around software that is entirely accessible to the general public (e.g. from the Apache Foundation). The concept is that the community can create new functionality in an ‘openlaws lab’ where developers can write enrichment tools/code (software) around code (law).

An important aspect of the system will be usability and user experience design. The best service is useless if users cannot work with it. A responsive design will ensure that the platform can be accessed on different devices, such as personal computers, tablets and smart phones. Accessibility features will make sure that access barriers are lowered as far as possible.

4.5 SWOT Analysis

The SWOT analysis provides an overview of the strengths and weaknesses of the venture and the opportunities and threats that it faces.⁴³

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Data as a free resource • User community involvement • First mover advantage • International partner network • High growth opportunities based on the potential market size • Open source software architecture • Innovative technologies can be introduced in the legal market • Supported by the European Commission (DG Justice) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many different stakeholders involved • No clear standards for the exchange of legal information established yet⁴⁴ • Aggregation and integration of different national databases is complicated

⁴³ This analysis will be extended in the final openlaws business model deliverable.

⁴⁴ Metalex and Akoma Ntoso are established standards.

Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More legal databases become available as open data as a result of the PSI Directive • Better standardization (ELI/ECLI) • Better structured metadata available • Progress in research on semantics, linked open data and big data analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community not participating in the platform • Member States building competing similar solutions • Content providers not joining the network

Table 2: SWOT Analysis

4.6 SLEPT Analysis

The SLEPT analysis provides a picture of the social, legal, economic, political and technological framework in which openlaws operates.⁴⁵

Social	
Open innovation	User needs are at the core of development of new services and new business models. The trend of creating and integrating communities via open innovation is an opportunity for openlaws.
Legal network	There have been several attempts to create social networks in the legal market. However, the comprehensive network of legal content around which the legal expert community and citizens and businesses are created is a novelty.
Social entrepreneurship	‘Doing well by doing good’ is not a contradiction anymore. Social entrepreneurship is considered as a new discipline in economics. By providing free legal information services as part of the business model, openlaws can be described as a social entrepreneurship venture. The offering of premium legal services for businesses and legal professionals makes the venture sustainable.
Legal ⁴⁶	
Copyright	Legislation and case law are exempt from copyright protection in many countries and are increasingly made accessible as open data under the PSI Directive. On the other hand, user-generated content within the openlaws platform will be published under a Creative Commons license. Premium content of commercial publishers may be linked (via open APIs).
Privacy	Users can decide whether or not their profiles and their own generated contents are public or not. Personal information contained in case law will be processed as originally published by the official national

⁴⁵ This analysis will be extended in the final openlaws business model deliverable.

⁴⁶ Legal aspects of public sector information are also subject to research by the LAPSI 2.0 EU project, <http://www.lapsi-project.eu> (26.6.2015).

	databases.
Economic	
Valuable legal market	Traditionally, the legal market is highly valuable, since access to law is often complicated and the risk in legal disputes is often high. Accordingly, experts can charge high hourly rates and associated services like legal literature and value-added legal databases are expensive as well.
Large market	Law affects each and every person and company. This means the market size is big (500 million EU citizens, 21 million businesses within the EU).
Economies of scale	Using ICT tools enables legal experts and end-users to use economies of scale, e.g. by sharing legal information. This is still rather rare in the legal market, where the ‘wheel is often re-invented’ for every single case.
Free	<i>Chris Anderson</i> has described the power of ‘Free’ ⁴⁷ and basic legal information is supposed to be free by its very nature. Innovative business models can offer free services for one user group, while charging elsewhere (e.g. power users).
SME business model innovation	openlaws is building an innovative business model with open data as a free resource and the communities of legal professionals, businesses and citizens as open innovation contributors
Political	
Access to justice	Access to legislation and case law is a fundamental principle in democratic countries. Today’s ICT tools can help to make such access easier for citizens, businesses and legal experts in order to foster collaboration, transparency and accountability.
Open government	Governments are opening their databases and make legislation and case law available as open data so that it can be re-used by other services.
Digital Agenda	The Digital Agenda and the Innovative Union as flagship initiatives under the Europe 2020 growth strategy support open data and open innovation ventures.
Technological	
Open data	Legislation and case law are made available as open data and can be used as a free resource in a business model.
Open source	Open source software is another (usually free) resource that can be

⁴⁷ Anderson, Chris (2009). *Free: The Future of a Radical Price*. New York: Hyperion. ISBN 978-1-4013-2290-8.

software	used in the creation of new innovative services and business models. Open source software is often more stable and professional than closed software.
Visualization	Typically legal information is represented as simple text. However, new technological developments allow for better visualization of large amounts of text and their relations.

Table 3: SLEPT Analysis

4.7 Risk Assessment and Contingency Plans

Risk and opportunity are the two sides of the same coin. While there are opportunities for large growth and innovative solutions, there are also risks related to starting the openlaws venture and to making it sustainable in the long run.

- The platform requires network effects in order to work properly. Without a community of legal professionals, businesses and citizens the chances for success are low. As a contingency measure the platform will be designed in a way so that users can work with legal content on a standalone basis, even if there are no other partners for collaboration.
- Content is king and this is also true for a legal information platform. While the public sector is legally obliged to provide data under the PSI directive, private companies do not have to join openlaws, if they do not want to. In order to get content providers on board, solutions will be developed so that publishers and other providers can promote their premium legal content.
- From a European perspective there is a risk that US-based IT companies rush into the market, offer a similar solution and then dominate it. This would not only be a drawback for openlaws, but also for the European Union and its Member States. European law should remain in European hands, especially if the European legal community is part of the system. The only counter-measure is to move ahead swiftly and to keep the first mover advantage.

There are further bottlenecks and challenges that need to be addressed and properly solved. In particular the 24 official languages within the 28 Member States of the European Union can be hard to handle. Furthermore, the integration of the different databases from the different jurisdictions needs to be addressed in the system architecture. The task here is similar to those of other content aggregators in other industries.

5 Market Study

5.1 Market Players

Legal tech is located at an intersection between governmental systems, NGOs, traditional publishers and the new economy, as illustrated in figure 7.

Figure 14: Legal Tech Market Intersection

5.1.1 Governments

The rule of law is a fundamental pillar of every democracy. Since the mid-1990s, many countries have been offering legal databases to inform their citizens. While many databases are offered for free, others still have restricted access. As a consequence of the PSI directive, this will hopefully change soon.

Examples of open databases are EUR-Lex by the Publication Office/the European Commission, RIS in Austria, Legislation.gov.uk in the UK, Gesetze im Internet in Germany, and many others around the world.

EUR-Lex and the Member State databases are stand-alone databases. This means they are not linked in any way. The ELI and ECLI identifiers may be useful in the future to refer from one database to another, but a fully integrated system that is creating linked open data sets and semantic analysis over different jurisdictions requires one database. As this is precisely the objective of the openlaws project, the BOLDbase will enable comparative legal research and networking over the EU and Member States at the same time.

The same is true for N-Lex. N-Lex provides a joint interface for legislation in the different EU Member States. Contrary to openlaws.eu N-Lex does not aggregate the contents of the databases but directs the user query to the selected database. While this has the advantage that not all the data needs to be hosted and duplicated, the data cannot be linked or analysed. From the openlaws.eu user survey and log files from the Austrian RIS connector we know that N-Lex is hardly ever used.

5.1.2 NGOs

There are non-governmental organisations with the aim to make the law available to everybody for free. The most prominent example is probably the Free Access to Law Movement (FALM).⁴⁸ A full list of the organisations that have joined the declaration on Free Access to Law is available on the FALM website. Many members in different countries have adopted the name “Legal Information Institute (LII)”. While these organisations share the common aim of free access to law, they operate usually rather independently and in different ways. This means that the users of LII systems often will only get access to the legislation and

⁴⁸ <http://www.fatlm.org> (26.6.2015).

case law of one country.

5.1.3 Publishers

Historically, information services in the legal field have been provided by publishers. They have printed legal textbooks, which were and are used by legal experts. Today, these publishers offer the most prominent legal ICT services. Three of the largest players are Thomson Reuters, Reed Elsevier/Lexis Nexis and Wolters Kluwer. Publishers often apply traditional business models and are used to selling their premium content to experts. Premium content usually refers to legal literature, which is written by experts.

The business model for publishers is quite different to that of new legal tech companies. Their models are designed around content. New tech companies often provide new functionality independent of content. Even if both sides are moving towards a common ground, it is likely that the gap will continue to exist. Take for example document sharing: just like the music industry always wanted to avoid file sharing, typical publishers do not want to create networks between legal experts, because they prefer to maintain their one-to-many business model. Having observed the disappearing of Encyclopaedia Britannica, they are not supporting Wikipedia-like services either.

This is an opportunity for new legal tech entrants. In the USA there are already a few new and full-blooded legal tech services, like for example Rocket Lawyer. They use standardization and ICT services to provide customers with personalized contracts, without having to search an expensive database and without having to pay for an expensive lawyer.

5.1.4 New Economy

Even though publishers are highly specialized, the services of the new economy are increasingly used also by the rather conservative legal professionals, simply because they provide excellent functionality for little or for no money. Experts regularly use Google to search public legal databases because the user interface of the database itself is too complex and because the Google search delivers better search results. Companies and citizens are looking for lawyers in LinkedIn, rather than in old-fashioned directories of local legal expert associations. Documents are sent via e-mail or shared between lawyer and client via Dropbox, because of the simplicity and effectiveness – even if security cannot always be guaranteed. Customers get informed in discussion forums or legal wikis (even if these are not as sophisticated as in the medical sector – not yet).

This means that new economy market players are moving into the legal market. In many cases they have powerful technology and functionality, but they are not focused on legal content (because for them this might be a niche with relatively high entry barriers because of the complexity of the subject).

5.2 Geographical Market

The potential geographic market of openlaws is the world. Exceptions are of course countries where there is no constitutional state, where the exercise of governmental power is not constrained by the law. In other words: If there are laws, there is a right to exist for openlaws.

There are of course differences in legal systems, for example between continental European system and Anglo-American systems. However, on an abstract level, there is almost always legislation, case law, legal literature/commentary and acting persons. These are the pillars of openlaws.eu as described above.

The challenge is to integrate the law from the various countries in the BOLDbase. One main

task is therefore to design a simple yet powerful mechanism to connect to many legal data sources rapidly.

Under the openlaws.eu project, three country case studies are conducted for the UK, the Netherlands and for Austria. Furthermore, a case study on the European Union has been completed.⁴⁹ These are also the countries that are integrated for the prototype of the openlaws.eu platform (TRL 6).

5.3 Porter Five Forces

The five forces analysis is a framework to analyse the level of competition within an industry. Based on this the attractiveness of a specific industry can be estimated. The five forces analysis was created by Michael E. Porter and has become a useful and popular instrument for many business plans.

Figure 15: Porter Five Forces

5.3.1 Bargaining Power of Suppliers

Primary content (legislation and case law) is typically provided by public bodies. Even though they are the authors of this content, legislation and case law are exempt from copyright protection in most countries. However, the databases containing it are protected. The trend towards open data (PSI directive) creates a window of opportunity for new providers, as this content is available at no or very low cost.

Publishers own the rights in existing secondary content (legal literature). Their negotiating power for this content is high. Copyright on content is a monopoly. However, publishers want to sell their content in the best way. Besides, even if commentary by one publisher/author is not available, this does not mean that there is no content on the same legal question by another author (provided by another publisher). In addition, the obligation in many funded projects is more and more that content has to be published under an open-access regime.

The power of individual legal experts publishing content is low. Usually there is a “competition” also in the research area. Academics as well as lawyers want to publish fast in order to be the first to write on a subject-matter (because this often means more citations which equals a higher impact). The exceptions are authors with a high reputation, such as

⁴⁹ See OpenLaws.eu deliverables D1.2.d2 – EU Case Study and D1.2.d3 – United Kingdom Case Study.

some professors of famous law schools.

Software suppliers are in a relatively weak position. There are many (open source) software solutions on which legal tech services can be built.

5.3.2 *Bargaining Power of Customers*

Legal experts require high quality and are used to pay high prices for legal content, either in print or in form of databases. They are rather reluctant to adopt new solutions. Lawyers in the EU are still often solo-practitioners, even though there is a clear trend towards establishing larger law firms. Larger law firms are in a stronger negotiation position. The same is true for administrations and universities as customers of legal information services.

Customers have only a limited choice between solutions when it comes to access to legislation and case law. Typically there are free governmental databases with primary sources and limited functionality and then there is an oligopoly of a few publishers selling premium content and providing advanced functionality. The bargaining power of customers grows with an increasing number of free Internet services that can be used as substitute products.

5.3.3 *Threat of Substitute Products*

Legal experts are starting to use services from ICT suppliers like Google, LinkedIn, Dropbox, and others. However, these services are designed for the broad public and not catered to the specific needs of legal professionals. These substitute products often work as a fast entry point, especially when searching for legal information on a very broad scale. The more specific a request is, the higher the need for a specialized solution becomes. This was also confirmed in the openlaws.eu survey as well as in expert interviews.

5.3.4 *Threat of New Entrants*

Entry barriers to the legal tech market are relatively high, so the risk of new entrants is rather low. The challenge is that new entrants need to have a sound understanding of ICT and legal knowledge at the same time. The typical legal expert has insufficient expertise to design an IT service and the typical software engineer will lack the in-depth know-how in the area of law the service is meant to address. This interdisciplinary requirement keeps the barrier high.

Reputation and quality of service are additional barriers that new entrants need to master. In an environment that is currently dominated by governmental providers and an oligopoly of legal publishers with a long history, an excellent track record and endless amounts of premium legal content, it is hard to define new compelling customer propositions.

5.3.5 *Competitive Rivalry within the Legal Market*

Based on the relatively high entry barriers and the rather well-established structures in the legal ICT market, the rivalry in the market is moderate. There is however a certain tension between governmental services and publishers.

Governments are not supposed to compete in the market with private companies. On the other hand, informing citizens about the law is a fundamental task of a government, as already described several times before in this and related reports. In order to make the law available to citizens, governments have to use a distribution channel. In former times this was print format. The move to free governmental online databases has already led to discussions and even legal actions because publishers argued that governments would interfere with the market and take away the business of publishing companies and their commercial online

databases.⁵⁰ Today it is not disputed anymore that governments should operate their own free databases. The boarder line usually is: Governments provide “basic” services while publishers provide “premium” services. This line is moving over time. Features that were considered “advanced” in the past may be rather “basic” today.

5.3.6 Sixth Force: Complementors

Complementors are considered to be the “sixth” force in the market. In the smartphone industry complementors are for example apps and covers. In the legal information industry, complementary products to primary sources are literature and commentary by legal experts, but also preparatory works. As mentioned before, this is the domain of legal publishers. New entrants do not have this network of complementary content.

5.4 Market Valuation

The market of legal information is split in the non-commercial governmental part and the commercial part. While no “numbers” for the first part are available (access to justice as a public good), there are numbers for the latter:

According to MarketLine industry reports, the accumulated revenue of Thomson Reuters, Reed Elsevier/Lexis Nexis and Wolters Kluwer amounts to approx. 10 billion EUR per year. Access to legal expert databases ranges between 250 and 1000 EUR per unit per user per year, but can also be significantly higher. Legal file management and communication software is often sold for 5,000 to 10,000 EUR per user, and combined with SLAs, charging 10% or more per year. The global market for legal services as such (i.e. services provided by legal professionals) amounts to over 800 billion EUR per year on a global level and to over 250 billion EUR in Europe (UK, Germany, Italy, Spain and France account for almost 65% of the European market). The compound annual growth rate in the legal services market in the upcoming years is predicted to be 3.6%.⁵¹

6 Organizational Plan

6.1 openlaws gmbh

As a result of the first phase of the openlaws research studies, the ‘openlaws gmbh’ was incorporated as an Austrian limited company (Gesellschaft mit beschränkter Haftung, GmbH). The purpose of the spin-off is the operation of openlaws and to implement the business plan in order to make the project sustainable beyond the openlaws.eu project duration. While the openlaws.eu project is focused on the creation of a ‘big open legal data (BOLD)’ vision for the European Commission (DG Justice) and the prototype implementation (TRL 6), the spin-off company will focus on the growth of the community across Europe and the operational sustainability of the venture with a fully operational platform (TRL 9).

⁵⁰ This has happend for example in Austria where the government was sued by one of the large Austrian publishers.

⁵¹ MarketLine Industry Profile (2012), Legal Services in Europe, Reference Code: 0201-0423; MarketLine Industry Profile (2012), Global Legal Services, Reference Code: 0199-0423, <http://www.marketline.com> (26.6.2015).

Figure 16: Strategic Phases of openlaws

The company is located in Salzburg/Austria and is a subsidiary of the openlaws.eu project partner BY WASS GmbH. The company will employ software developers who can take the openlaws.eu prototype to a usable product that can survive in the market.

6.2 openlaws Research

Universities and research institutes are invited to use the BOLDbase beyond the EU project in accordance with the open innovation approach. This invitation is not limited to the existing research partners, but it is open to everybody. In consideration of access to the entire aggregated database, research partners will only be asked for a contribution to cover the operating costs of the platform.

Governments can become part of this framework as well. They are asked to connect their national databases with openlaws. Once the national databases are connected, users can benefit from the integration of national and European legislation and case law immediately.

6.3 openlaws Community

In an open innovation setting, the community is part of the organization. With a growing community it will become soon necessary to manage the community. This can be either organized at a central level, or certain experienced users within the community can be appointed as administrators of certain groups.

At this stage, it is still too early to make too many assumptions. A community is a living thing and its behaviour is hard to predict. Once the first prototype has been launched, the system will be adjusted to the user needs. This includes community management mechanisms.

We will approach the community in five main steps, as suggested by Benjamin Edelman in the Harvard Business Review:

Amass a large user base	Offer stand-alone value	Recruit marquee users	Reduce users' risks	Ensure compatibility with legacy systems
Leverage existing user groups	Add a service that is useful even if few others join the platform	Pay them to join	Offer pay-as-you-go pricing	Offer just enough compatibility to attract new users
Use publicly available data as a substitute for one user group		Buy the marquee brand	Subsidize early users	Anticipate resistance from legacy systems

Table 4: The Platform Builder's Checklist⁵²

⁵² Benjamin Edelman (2015), How to launch your digital platform, <https://hbr.org/2015/04/how-to-launch-your-digital-platform> (26.6.2015).

7 Marketing Plan

In general terms, marketing refers to what an organisation must do to create and exchange value with customers. Often people think that marketing is merely advertising in the sense of promotion, but this view is by far too narrow. Marketing is a complex task and helps to bring innovation to the users. According to Peter Drucker, there are only two basic functions of any venture: Marketing and innovation.

With the openlaws platform, an innovation in the area of legal information tools is being created. The task for the spin-off company is to bring this innovation to the users. The following figure shows the complexity of the marketing process:

Figure 17: Schematic of Marketing Process⁵³

The “5Cs” (customers, company, competitors, collaborators, context) have already been described above. This leads us to the “4Ps” (product, place, promotion, price).

7.1 Product

The product for openlaws.eu will consist of three parts:

- Free legal search via the web interface
- Premium advanced legal search via the web interface
- Aggregated data from the BOLDbase via connectors

As mentioned earlier, the outcome of the EU project will be a prototype (TRL 6). This prototype will then have to be developed in a follow-up project.

⁵³ Alvin J. Silk (2006), What Is Marketing, Harvard Business School Press.

7.2 Price

Free access to law is a prerequisite of the project. The first and most important reason is: In a democracy everybody should have access to the law. This is a main difference to other free services on the web. Often users expect that certain services are free just because the market has come up with those free services. This is a result of competition, not because of a human right. For a legal information service this is different. But this leads us also to the second reason. The second reason is actually competition. Competition with free governmental databases. If there was no free part of openlaws, users would probably stick with the free services.

Premium advanced legal search services are usually not offered by governments. This is the domain of legal publishers. While openlaws might come up with advanced features in the future, there are currently no ambitions to build these internally. The open innovation approach is rather to work with others and let them build what they think is best. This way, the project will also not interfere with the business of existing market players, but rather help them to provide better services. Prices for these services are likely to be in line with today's market prices.

Access to the aggregated BOLDbase will be the main revenue stream for openlaws.eu. This income should make the platform sustainable. This means that publishers, research projects, governments, legal tech companies etc. have to pay in order to get access to the structured data via interfaces. In this initial business model it is still not possible to give a prediction of the target price, as this will be defined by the future infrastructure and operational costs, that are currently not known yet. Estimated Return-On-Investment (ROI) and Net-Present-Value (NPV) can also only be calculated, once price and costs are defined.

7.3 Place and Distribution

The distribution channel for openlaws.eu is the Internet. The services is designed as a web service so that it can scale and deal with users from different jurisdictions. An offline system would have a few advantages (e.g. when there is no Internet coverage in a court room), but the advantages of online connectivity are obvious. There is only one system to maintain, users can work together, data is accessed online and it is not necessary to store big amounts of data on local devices.

The website to access the free search will be www.openlaws.eu. Potential premium services will be offered under www.openlaws.com. Access to the BOLDbase will be possible via a webservice.

7.4 Promotion

openlaws will be promoted on different levels:

Category	Promoter
EU	DG Justice Council, working group Open Innovation Strategy Policy Group (OISPG) CORDIS Related EU research projects
EU Member States	National governments and administrations (focus AT, UK, NL)

Legal professionals	European bar association (CCBE) European notaries
Businesses	National chambers of commerce (focus AT, UK, NL)
Citizens	National workers council associations (focus AT, UK, NL)
Research	International legal informatics and e-government conferences
Publishers	National and international publishers
Social media & web	Twitter, Facebook, Wikipedia

8 Implementation Plan

Reference is made to WS3 of the project.

Figure 18: openlaws Implementation (PERT)

While the prototype of openlaws has been implemented throughout the openlaws.eu project, the development to final market readiness is done by the project spin-off.

9 Operations Plan

Openlaws.eu is currently a EU project where four university partners and two SMEs work together. This research character is supposed to change after the end of the project. However, partnerships with open data providers, the EU, Member States and other partners will continue to play a key role in the operation of the platform.

Figure 19: openlaws Main Process Map

The main processes of openlaws are (processes closer to the users are mentioned first):

- **Website operation:** The user interface on the web is the closest relation to the user. A user-friendly interface and responsive web design are essential.
- **Web services operation:** Third party developers will access the BOLDbase via web services. A clear interface and a good documentation are essential.
- **Support:** Users will have questions and errors will occur, regardless of how good a system has been implemented. Support services are essential for customer satisfaction.
- **Marketing & sales:** Currently WS4 deals with the (scientific) dissemination and user community engagement (early adopters). Once the platform has reached the operational level (TRL 9), sales and marketing activities will be necessary. A special focus will be put on social marketing campaigns.
- **Product development:** The BOLDbase and the free search provide the basis for additional product development, such as advanced expert features. The usage and integration of open source software components will continue to play a main role.
- **Open data integration:** With more legal databases connected, the value of the platform will grow.
- **Infrastructure operation:** Hosting of the platform is a system-critical part of the operation. A priority will be given to hosting solutions in the EU, mainly for privacy reasons.
- **Research:** Legal informatics is a complicated area and requires on-going research activities with universities, research institutes and users.
- **Strategic management:** As for any venture, strategic management is necessary to set the direction and to decide how the venture can go from here to there.
- **Financial administration:** Controlling and accounting are essential components for the sustainability of the venture.

- **Personnel management:** An innovation is only as good as the actors implementing it. A product idea can be changed and adapted. The right team is harder to replace.
- **Open innovation management:** The core team will receive support from external partners who provide knowledge, data, innovative ideas, feedback, resources, etc. Such partners can be users, legal professionals, public bodies, universities, software development communities, the media, etc.

10 Outlook

The end of the openlaws.eu project, supported by DG Justice, is just the beginning of the implementation of the business model for openlaws. During the project the team has spent time and effort on investigation about how a venture with a social impact – namely better access to justice – can be made sustainable. Legal information is a precious “public good” in every democracy and citizens and businesses should know their rights and obligations. This is also key in European Union, where the law should not be used to build walls, but rather to form a common single market.

However, if providing access to law is a such an important public task, then shouldn't it be up to governments and European institutions? And don't they do it already to a sufficient extent? While one can always argue about the right quality, the simple answer to the question is: Yes, they do. Even better, as a result of the PSI directive, the EU and its member states provide the information as open data, allowing others to build new and innovative solutions on top of primary legislation and case law.

The research of openlaws.eu has shown that there are many ideas and potential applications to make access to justice easier. This includes the value that is created by the openlaws.eu platform. The community can contribute information, which is beneficial for others.

Whenever value is created, a smaller part of such value can be captured for the purpose of ensuring the continuation of this value-generation process. This is what business models do. They describe the way how value is built and the mechanisms to maintain the venture.

In today's Internet economy, a predominant business model for cloud services has emerged. So called “freemium” services offer free services to the general public, while premium services are provided to paying customers. Criticism on free services exists of course, arguing that whenever something is free, then “the user is the product” that is being sold elsewhere. While this – unfortunately – may be true in many cases, it is not a given fact that it has to be this way. In the area of open source software or in the area of Creative Commons works, people are voluntarily making software code or other works (photographs, publications) available for free. So people are voluntarily giving, without asking for an immediate return. Perhaps just hoping, that somebody else will give something back in return. For some people it is hard to understand the motivation behind this concept, but it is a given fact that it exists.

For a business, the situation is different of course. In order to run a venture, bills have to be paid. Cost drivers for IT companies are salaries and IT infrastructure costs (even though becoming cheaper, the costs can be still very high, depending on the traffic and storage). In addition, tax has to be paid, even if it the company is a venture with a social purpose. Tax money is of course the income of the EU and its member states, which makes it possible to develop public legal information systems and open data interfaces. A social venture has no tax income, only tax payments. It has to rely on other sources of income to make the venture sustainable.

Freemium is way to generate income. Such model has to be transparent enough so that users do not become the product and do not even get the impression of becoming the product. Such trust can only be built over time and with a lot of transparency and communication. Instead, it should be a common joint effort, where users see and understand that money is needed to operate the service.

One example is Wikipedia of course. People reveal information for free, know that their knowledge is “the product” and understand that donations are necessary to pay for the infrastructure of Wikipedia.

openlaws is no Wikipedia of course. Replicating a model like Wikipedia and building large networks is one of the most challenging activities. Also, the legal community is much smaller compared to the general public. For example, there are 8 million citizens in Austria, but only 6,000 lawyers. When it comes to legal informatics, the situation becomes even more tense. The number of people who can code AND have the sufficient knowledge about the law is very limited. Such people usually work at legal information departments at universities or for legal publishers.

For these reasons, a slightly different model has been chosen for the openlaws spin-off company, which was incorporated in 2015 in Austria. While an ongoing stream of donations or – even better – a payment by each and every lawyer (see CanLII case study) would be preferred, it is just no option for the time being. Therefore, the solution is to offer free services for the general public, while the more advanced features are premium features under a subscription payment model. This ensures that the general public has better access to law, while the experts and large business users with legal departments will pay for the service (e.g. for closed group functionality). In our view, this is a fair model, because those who make money with legal information already will be able to provide their services better and faster. Capturing part of this value to operate openlaws and to sustain the free part is a viable way for doing good and doing well at the same time.

In November 2015 the openlaws spin-off received ODI start-up status. The ODI (Open Data Institute) was founded by Sir Tim Berners-Lee and Sir Nigel Shabolt. The institute promotes the usage and creation of open data. With the ODI as a strategic partner, openlaws is confident that a sustainable business can be created, which also has a positive social impact in Europe. Even beyond the openlaws.eu project.

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